

Systemic Shocks and Multi-level Economic Policies

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Introduction

The past two decades have been characterized by several systemic shocks (financial crisis; great recession; Eurozone sovereign debt crisis; pandemic recession; inflation; Ukraine war and global geopolitical instability) and the investigation of the most appropriate economic policies in a multi-level governance is crucial to improve the dynamic of the economic systems especially in the European and Italian scenario.

Several research projects address quite different topics and all the theoretical and empirical results are strongly policy oriented. The main research topics under investigation are the following: (i) the determinant of public debt sustainability; (ii) the future of Eurozone/EU beyond PEPP and NGEU; (iii) the real impact of Central Bank monetary policies; (iv) the relationship between corruption and public expenditure; (v) the impact of shocks on youth labour market performance; (vi) uncertainty and cryptocurrency; (vii) the nature of inflation and the impact of monetary policies; (viii) toward a sustainable sustainability?; other research projects are now in progress.

Methods

A wide set of methods are use according to the different topics above mentioned. The use of multisectoral models and computational approaches are useful in topics (i), (iii) and (vii), econometric strategies are appropriate in topics (v) and (vi) while a narrative/descriptive approach theoretically founded is adopted for topics (ii) and (viii).

Some investigations are new research questions partly based on previous and already published results, as showed in Reference list.

Results

All theoretical and, especially, empirical results are crucial for defining better multi-level economic policies in a complex and dynamic global/European scenario. Favoring detailed design of fiscal, monetary and regulation policies are of crucial importance to address shocks and to favor a more sustainable economic and social path of development.

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